

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT: Using a variety of modern methods in teaching English to young school-age children, it was discussed the development of students' logical thinking skills and the ability of students to find and answer quickly and correctly during quick questions and answers.

Key Words: IELTS program, historical, ethnic, cultural, socio-pedagogical, primary school, teaching methods, game, modern, methodology, English

INTRODUCTION

We all know today that in the teaching of the English language, not only in many other disciplines, but also in other situations, there are more and more talented specialists who are able to go out in any situation. The reason for this is that a teacher with a strong methodology is able to assess any situation correctly and is able to draw his own conclusions. Also, first of all, every teacher should have a methodology. Especially when teaching elementary school. Our people have always had such sayings. No matter which way you grow the seedlings, they will not grow. We call it the teachers' methodology, but very few people now understand what the methodology is.

1. PROPOSED WORK

The origins of the methodology go back to the practical activities of the people. one who has mastered the technique of doing something can do so easily and quickly compared to others. A person who does not know the method will spend a lot of time and effort to do it. The methodology can be practical or theoretical in

nature. Method (Greek — *metodos* — way of knowing or researching, theory, teaching) is a method of practical application of reality, assimilation, study, guidelines for learning, a set of methods, and the creation and foundation of philosophical knowledge.

IMPLEMENTATION OF ENCRYPTION

The origins of the methodology go back to the practical activities of the people. One who has mastered the technique of doing something can do so easily and quickly compared to others. A person who does not know the method will spend a lot of time and effort to do it. The methodology can be practical or theoretical in nature. The methods of human activity depend on the understanding of the laws of reality. The doctrine of M.s is called methodology in science. Man first accumulated his knowledge of reality by observing, comparing, contrasting, and distinguishing things and events around him. With the development of the sciences of reality, the guidelines and methods used in the sciences have also improved. Practical (empirical) and theoretical methods of science have emerged. One of the reasons for the Republic of Uzbekistan is the Resolution of the First President of Uzbekistan No. PP-1875 of December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the study of foreign languages." According to the three resolutions, in order to further strengthen the teaching of foreign languages, mainly English, from primary school to English, it is doubtful that English lessons from 1st grade in all secondary schools should be taught in a variety of forms of entertainment. The transition from the 2nd grade to the teaching of the alphabet, reading and grammar through modern, innovative, various game methods has begun.

Recently, the number of people learning English is growing. This is due to the fact that in the process of life it is becoming more and more difficult to do something without knowing English. But language learning also depends on the age. Even young scientists have proven that children can quickly learn the language of

adults²⁷. It is especially useful to teach young children in English through a variety of methods in the primary school. For example, by teaching them to memorize 10-15 words from a dictionary, in the next lesson they will be asked in an unusual way, rather than asking for those words in the traditional way. Asking them memorized words in a playful way is very helpful in memorizing English words. In addition, speaking English without grammar is a problem for many, as exemplified by the fact that the highly developed IELTS program is becoming increasingly important in speaking, listening and writing. In addition, the teaching of English in preschool education is increasing day by day, and some children who are now entering primary school speak English fluently. That's why we have to teach elementary school in a different way than usual. As another example, during the lesson we have to explain to them in different ways. For example, this method is very useful if you use interesting words on the cards, compose questions using the words that elementary school students know, distribute them and get immediate answers. Or the explanation on the monitor will stay in the minds of students. The use of such methods is called the use of modern technology. We need to spread these methods among schoolchildren as soon as possible.

In the process of teaching English today, the problem of developing creative abilities in primary school students is becoming a particularly pressing issue. In the modern conditions of the pedagogical process of secondary schools, this is an important scientific problem of historical, ethnic, cultural and socio-pedagogical significance. Today, Uzbekistan is one of the countries striving to take its rightful place in the world community. In order to create such facilities, it is very important for our people, who are building the great future of Uzbekistan in cooperation with foreigners, to know the importance of perfect knowledge of languages. Its development is a useful way not only for the younger generation, but for all.

Clearly, we need to pay more attention to the education of the younger generation, as well as to the education of the younger generation. As mentioned above, the

methodology and work of leading experts or teachers in any subject or field is very important.

2. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, teaching in the primary grades is both difficult and difficult for every teacher. It is especially difficult to teach English to primary school students. Therefore, it will be easier to teach English to primary school students using a variety of methods.

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